

An Efficient Hardware design and Implementation of Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) Algorithm

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Abstract - We propose an efficient hardware architecture design & implementation of Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). The AES algorithm defined by the National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) of United States has been widely accepted. The cryptographic algorithms can be implemented with software or built with pure hardware. However Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) implementation offers quicker solution and can be easily upgraded to incorporate any protocol changes. This contribution investigates the AES encryption cryptosystem with regard to FPGA and Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description language (VHDL). Optimized and Synthesizable VHDL code is developed for the implementation of 128-bit data encryption process. AES encryption is designed and implemented in FPGA, which is shown to be more efficient than published approaches. Xilinx ISE 12.3i software is used for simulation. Each program is tested with some of the sample vectors provided by NIST and output results are perfect with minimal delay. The throughput reaches the value of 1609Mbit/sec for encryption process with Device XC6vlx240t of Xilinx Virtex Family.

Keywords- Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Rinjdael, Cryptography, FPGA, Throughput.

I. INTRODUCTION

To protect the data transmission over insecure channels two types of cryptographic systems are used: Symmetric and Asymmetric cryptosystems. Symmetric cryptosystems such as Data Encryption Standard (DES) [1], 3 DES, and Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) [4], uses an identical key for the sender and receiver; both to encrypt the message text and decrypt the cipher text. Asymmetric cryptosystems such as Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) & Elliptic Curve Cryptosystem (ECC) uses different keys for encryption. Symmetric cryptosystem is more suitable to encrypt large amount of data with high speed. To replace the old Data Encryption Standard, in Sept 12 of 1997, the National Institute of Standard Technology (NIST) required proposals to what was called Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). Many algorithms were presented originally with researches from 12 different nations. Fifteen algorithms were selected to the Round one. Next five were chosen to the Round two. Five algorithms finalized by NIST are MARS, RC6, RIJNDAEL [2], SERPENT and TWOFISH [3]. On October 2nd 2000, NIST [4] has announced the Rijndael algorithm is the best in security, performance, efficiency, implement ability, & flexibility. The Rijndael algorithm was developed by Joan Daemen

of Proton World International and Vincent Rijmen of Katholieke University at Leuven. AES encryption is an efficient scheme for both hardware and software implementation. As compare to software implementation, hardware implementation provides greater physical security and higher speed. Hardware implementation is useful in wireless security like military communication and mobile telephony where there is a greater emphasis on the speed of communication. Most of the work has been presented on hardware implementation of AES using FPGA [5-9]. This paper presents efficient hardware architecture design & implementation of AES using FPGA and describes performance testing of Rijndael algorithm.

II. PREVIOUS DESIGN

An encryption algorithm converts a plain text message into cipher text message which can be recovered only by authorized receiver using a decryption technique. The AES-Rijndael algorithm [4] is an iterative private key symmetric block cipher. The input and output for the AES algorithm each consist of sequences of 128 bits (block length). Hence $N_b = \text{Block length}/32 = 4$. The Cipher Key for the AES algorithm is a sequence of 128, 192 or 256 bits (Key length). In this implementation we set the key length to 128. Hence $N_k = \text{Key length}/32 = 4$.

Fig. 1 AES Encryption process

A. Encryption Process:

The Encryption process consists of a number of different transformations applied consecutively over the data block bits, in a fixed number of iterations, called rounds. The number of rounds depends on the length of the key used for the encryption process. For key length of 128 bits, the number of iteration required are 10. (Nr = 10). As shown in Fig. 1, each of the first Nr-1 rounds consists of 4 transformations: SubBytes(), ShiftRows(), MixColumns() & AddRoundKey(). The four different transformations are described in detail below.

Sub Bytes Transformation: It is a non-linear substitution of bytes that operates independently on each byte of the State using a substitution table (S box). This S-box which is invertible is constructed by first taking the multiplicative inverse in the finite field GF (28) with irreducible polynomial $m(x) = x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x + 1$. The element {00} is mapped to itself. Then affine transformation is applied (over GF (2)).

Fig. 2 Look up table for S-box

Shift Rows Transformation: Cyclically shifts the rows of the State over different offsets. The operation is almost the same in the decryption process except for the fact that the shifting offsets have different values.

Mix Columns Transformation: This transformation operates on the State column-by-column, treating each column as a four-term polynomial. The columns are considered as polynomials over GF (28) and multiplied by modulo $x^4 + 1$ with a fixed polynomial $a(x) = \{03\}x^3 + \{01\}x^2 + \{02\}x$.

The function xtime is used to represent the multiplication with '02', modulo the irreducible polynomial $m(x) = x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x + 1$. Fig.3 illustrates the implementation of function $B=xtime(A)$, in which output bits 0,2,5,6,7 just correspond to input bits shifted and only 3 bits are modified by the XOR operation. Applying this concept, we can easily realize the 4-byte output of Mixcolumn as shown in Fig.4. This direct implementation takes 2 xtime and 4 additions in calculating each byte output using the module Byte_MixC whose operation is $2a \oplus 3b \oplus c \oplus d$. In our design, we express the operation of Byte_MixC as $2(a \oplus b) \oplus b \oplus (c \oplus d)$. So, an efficient design of MixColumn transformation is shown in Fig. 5. The new

architecture needs only 1 xtime and 4 additions operations for each Byte_MixC module.

Fig. 3 Function xtime

Fig. 4 Original 4-Byte MixColumn

Fig. 5 Proposed 4-Byte Mixcolumn

AddRoundKey transformation: This transformation is simply performed by XOR the state with the round key. In [2], the Key Expansion (KE) is realized as Fig. 6, where $K_{i+1,2}$ must wait until the result of $K_{i+1,3}$ is calculated and it needs 4 calculated steps to obtain the complete outputs of KE. Such design directly follows from

$$K_{i+1,0} = K_{i,0} \oplus F(K_{i,3})$$

$$K_{i+1,1} = K_{i+1,1} \oplus K_{i,1}$$

$$K_{i+1,2} = K_{i+1,2} \oplus K_{i,2}$$

$$K_{i+1,3} = K_{i+1,3} \oplus K_{i,3}$$

and we can reexpress above equation as

$$K_{i+1,1} = (K_{i,0} \oplus K_{i,1}) \oplus F(K_{i,3})$$

$$K_{i+1,2} = ((K_{i,0} \oplus K_{i,1}) \oplus K_{i,2}) \oplus F(K_{i,3})$$

$$K_{i+1,3} = ((K_{i,0} \oplus K_{i,1}) \oplus (K_{i,2} \oplus K_{i,3})) \oplus F(K_{i,3})$$

Based on this expression, we can develop a new key expansion module in which the output byte don't need to

wait the other output bytes. The proposed key expansion module is constructed and shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6 KE module in [2]

Fig. 7 Proposed KE module

It is known that the normal round includes the operations of SubByte, ShiftRow, Mixcolumn and AddRoundKey, and the final round is equal to the normal round without the MixColumn. Our architecture of AES encryptor is shown in Fig. 8. The final round in our design is just a operation of XOR with round key because SubByte and ShiftRow are the same as the normal round. Fig 9 shows the detailed design of AES encryptor where the control signals are described in Table 1 and Fig 10 depicts its entity diagram. It needs 10 cycles to finish AES encryption. Based on the same methodology of AES encryptor, an AES decryptor is also designed and integrated with the AES encryptor to yield a full functional AES en/decryptor.

Fig. 8 Architecture of AES Encryptor

Fig. 9 Proposed AES Encryptor design

1. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

All the results are based on simulations from the Xilinx ISE tools, using Test Bench Waveform Generator. All the individual transformation of encryption are simulated and synthesized using FPGA Vertex family and XC6v1x240t device. Pin configurations of AES Entity are shown in Table 2. Each program is tested with some of the sample vectors provided by NIST [4].

Fig. 10 Entity diagram of AES

TABLE 1 INPUT AND OUTPUT CONTROL SIGNALS

Pin Name	I/O Port	Pin Number (bit)	Pin Description
Clock	I	1	Chip clock
Reset	I	1	Clear all signal and data
Load	I	1	Load key and plaintext
Start	I	1	Start encryption process
Key_in	I	128	Key data bus
Data_in	I	128	Plaintext data
Kstat	O	1	Kstat becomes high before output comes
Qstrb	O	1	encryption is completed
Dstat	O	1	Dstat becomes high when plaintext is loaded, and low when Qstrb is high
Data_out	O	128	Cipher data bus

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